

COLLABORATIVE CONCEPT MAPPING IN ARCHITECTURAL EDUCATION

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The paper describes a pedagogic work, carried out in a School of Architecture, with a web-based learning environment that allows students to analyze texts in collaboration. This learning environment is based on the integration of three distinct components: 1. *A theoretical framework*, built up from 'theory bits' taken from different disciplines (architectural theory, linguistics, semiotics, graphic design, interface design) 2. *Individual and collaborative exercises*, designed to explore in a practical way the theoretical issues raised during the lectures. The exercises are individual (understanding and representing the content of a text with multimedia authoring software) and collaborative (building up a vocabulary and establishing relations between concepts, constructing a concept map) 3. *A web system*, with which students construct collaboratively the vocabulary and the concept map. Altogether, the intertwining of these three components, makes a case for a constructivist pedagogy supported by information and communication technologies.

1 Concept maps

Concept maps are graphic representations made up of nodes representing concepts connected by links. They are meant to reflect, in a synthetic manner, the knowledge structures that humans have in their minds. In this sense, a concept map can be thought of as a representation of a representation; a meta-representation which makes us aware of both *what* we know about a subject and *how* we know about it.¹

Besides being a representation of an individual's knowledge, a concept map also has a social dimension, in so far as it is a (visual) language to communicate ideas to others. Like any language, a concept map must have a *vocabulary* (a collection of symbols), a *syntax* (rules to combine them in sentences) and some *semantics* (a code to interpret sentences). With regard to the inner structuring of its language, a concept map can be a highly formal system of logic, or a highly informal ad-hoc utterance [9]. A rigid formalization of the concept map language might facilitate its implementation on the computer but, on the other hand, it might hinder individual expression. Like other languages, concept maps also need to balance objective rules with subjective expressiveness.

2 Constructivist pedagogy

According to constructivist theories of education, knowledge would not previously exist but rather, it would be the student who, with the guidance and support of the teacher, constructs it according to his or her own experience. For a constructivist pedagogy, concept maps appear to be an excellent technique to promote knowledge construction, both for individuals and groups. The application of concept mapping as learning technique can be traced back to the seminal work of Novak and Gowin [6]. Later on, its pedagogic implications were the object of intensive research.² According to Jonassen et al [3], concept maps are 'cognitive tools' that learners can use "to interpret and organize their unique solutions or personal knowledge, and represent what they have learned to others". Kommers [2] contends that concept mapping is an important learning technique because "it becomes more and more important to make students reflect on their own knowledge states, structure and perspectives".

¹ Obviously, the distinction between a mental schema and an external, visual representation (i.e. a concept map) which stands as a surrogate of it, raises some critical questions. The first has to do with the status of reality we attribute to the mental schema: we assume that it does exist even though we cannot provide objective evidence of it. If we accept the existence of both kinds of representation, mental and visual, there is still the question of the correspondence between both: it cannot be contended that a static, two-dimensional conceptual map accurately represents the dynamic, multidimensional knowledge structures of the mind. Finally, we have to consider that, in a cognitive act, the relations between mental and visual schemata are bi-directional: the concept map reflects how we are thinking about a particular issue and, in turn, the visual representation influences our thoughts.

² See Special Issue on Concept Mapping, *Journal of Interactive Learning Research*, 8 (3/4) (1997)

Concept mapping acquires its full pedagogic significance in a collaborative learning scenario, where both students and teachers participate in the construction of knowledge. Computer tools can support and enhance this collaboration, bringing about a qualitative change in education. Such is the assumption of Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning, CSCL, a research field concerned with the social, psychological, and epistemological transformations caused by the application of computers to education.³ This field is emerging as an area of research in its own right, following some pedagogic applications developed over the last fifteen years. Some of the most influential have been the communal database CSILE, designed to support intentional and collaborative learning in a network environment [7], and the Belvedere system [8], a shared workspace for coordinating and recording collaboration in scientific inquiry. Many other pedagogic applications of concept maps have been implemented in fields like biology, physics, mathematics, management and others.

3 Concept maps in Architecture: learning the aesthetic principles of Modern Architecture.

This pedagogic experience took place within the course 'SDR: Sistemas de Representación' (<http://www.salleurl.edu/sdr>), in the academic year 2000-01. One of the aims of the course is to integrate, in an innovative and meaningful manner, information and communication technologies into the education of Architecture. Therefore, the theoretical premises of the course conform to the nature of the web, where relationships between items become more important than the items themselves. In much the same way, the theoretical content of each one of the six themes that make up the course (TEXT, SHAPE, OBJECT, IMAGE, SPACE, and LIGHT) has been thought of as a network of relations between 'theory bits' taken from different disciplines. The theme TEXT, for instance, encompasses a variety of issues taken from different areas of knowledge, like linguistics (syntax and semantics, semantic triangle), cognition (semantic networks, concept maps), graphic design (posters, advertisement, media), interactive media (interface design, interactivity), and art and architectural theory (aesthetic principles of Modern Art and Architecture).

Along with the theoretical framework, a sequence of individual and collaborative exercises complete a constructivist pedagogic strategy⁴. The individual exercises are carried out with multimedia authoring software (DHTML, Flash). For the collaborative work, we have created the web-based system SDR: NETWORKING [TEXT], especially adapted to the needs of the course.

4 Development of the exercises

The sequence of the exercises is the following. At the outset, students are given five manifestoes of European avant-garde artists and architects of the beginning of the twentieth century (from Henry Van de Velde, Theo Van Doesburg, Walter Gropius, Mies van der Rohe, and Le Corbusier). Then, each student makes an interpretation of one text of his or her choice, and explains it to the class with a multimedia application (typically DHTML or Flash). Afterwards, they summarize the main ideas discovered in the manifesto in three concepts. Once the individual assignment is completed, the collaborative work begins. Students submit three concepts to the web system SDR: NETWORKING [TEXT], explaining their meanings in their own words (definitions directly taken from the dictionary would not do). As a result, a critical vocabulary, summarizing the main ideas of the five manifestoes -as interpreted by students- is collaboratively created by the class. Then, they can compare the different definitions of the concepts by browsing the vocabulary (Fig. 1). This way, students become aware of the relationships that exist between

³ <http://www.cscl2002.org/intro.html>

⁴ Tiessen and Ward [10] describe a pedagogic work, in which the interrelation of a *context* (designing playgrounds through geometric concepts), a *structure* (strategies to foster learning communities, like reciprocal teaching learning seminars and jigsaw classrooms) and a computer *medium* (the CSILE systems, a computer system which mediates shared spaces for collaboration) proved to be an effective strategy for knowledge building. In spite of the differences in goals and in the education level, the strategy we have adopted in our course, based on the interrelation between *theoretical framework*, *exercises* and *web system*, bears some resemblance to the one adopted by Tiessen and Ward. What is certainly common to both experiences is the belief that, to be an effective medium for education, a computer system must be coupled with a corresponding pedagogic methodology.

the different texts. Once they have become acquainted with the vocabulary, they establish relationships between pairs of concept definitions (Fig. 2). These relationships, collaboratively constructed by the class, are then visualized as a concept map (Fig. 3). The subsequent exploration of the semantic spaces embodied in the map becomes a source of knowledge, both for students and teachers. In this context, the conceptual map becomes an abstract machine, an artificial construct that allows learners to produce meaning in interaction with it.

5 SDR: NETWORKING [TEXT], a web-based collaborative environment

The web-based system SDR: NETWORKING [TEXT]⁵ has been especially designed for this course. It is divided in two environments: vocabulary and concept map.

5.1 Vocabulary

In the vocabulary environment (Fig. 1), students submit three concept definitions to the system using a form. As the vocabulary is being constructed collaboratively by the class, the list of words appears on the right-hand column. The size of the font indicates the number of definitions of a concept: the bigger the font, the larger the number of definitions.

Figure 1. Partial view of the vocabulary collectively created by the class, listed by concept definition.

Once the vocabulary has been completed, students can visualize concepts in different ways: 1. By concept, viewing all definitions of a particular concept, regardless of the text to which they are related. 2. By author, concentrating on concepts that are associated to a particular text. 3. By student, seeing all concepts introduced by each one of their peers.

However, for the information recorded in the system to become knowledge, simple browsing will not suffice. While they are exploring the vocabulary, students are expected to exercise their capacity to discern the different meanings assigned to the same concept, to relate concepts with similar connotations, and, fundamentally, to understand the ideas explained by others. To be sure that students have gone through this

⁵ SDR:NETWORKING [TEXT] is one of the six environments that altogether make up the web-based learning system of the course 'SDR: Sistemas de Representación'. For a detailed description of the system see: <http://www.salleurl.edu/sdr/info>

process of knowledge acquisition, we organize discussions in the classroom where they present and debate the ideas discovered in the vocabulary.

5.2 Concept map

Once the students know the vocabulary, we ask them to relate three pairs of concept definitions in the concept map environment. A simple interface allows them to define a relationship by only selecting two concept definitions in the lists of words displayed on the left and right (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Interface to establish relationships between concept pairs.

As the action of relating pairs of concept definitions is carried out by the class, a network of many-to-many relations between concept definitions is collaboratively created. This network of relationships, which represents the collective knowledge the class has gained from the interpretation of the five manifestoes, is graphically displayed as a concept map.

The concept map tool is straightforward and simple (Fig. 3). A concept map is constructed step by step, starting with the selection of a concept which becomes the 'focus node' of the map. Clicking on the node discloses the associated concepts. A color coding indicates to which of the five manifestoes the concept is related (i.e. Velde: yellow; Gropius:green;.....) Because of the limitations of the navigation space, the expansion of the network is limited to two levels. Then, to follow a thread of concepts, a new concept needs to be selected as focus node. When lines are selected on the concept map, the definitions of the two related concepts and the explanation of the relation are displayed at the bottom of the window.

Figure 3. Partial view of the concept map.

The concept map is the expression of an objectified knowledge which has been collectively created by the class.⁶ The visualization of the relationships between concepts facilitates understanding of the ideas contained in the five texts. Moreover, navigating through the concept map, students have the opportunity to further participate in the construction of knowledge. However, extracting knowledge from the concept map represents an intellectual challenge for the student. It is a process of knowledge elicitation which, as McAleese [4] argues, can be understood as a negotiation between what the student knows and the knowledge represented in the language of the map.⁷

6 Limitations of concept mapping

Different pedagogic experiences have warned against a methodology exclusively based on concept map construction. It has been demonstrated that the effectiveness of concept maps as learning tools improves when they are combined with other techniques [5]. Also, the ephemeral nature of the knowledge contained in a concept map is a limitation to take into account, because that knowledge is meaningful as long as a concept map is part of the course dynamics. However, it vanishes once the course is over and the students have neither the contextual knowledge nor the motivation to interact with the concept map.

To make up for such limitations, and as a conclusion of the series of exercises, we ask students to choose some portions of the concept map and to explain in a text the ideas they see in them. They are encouraged to make the diagram 'speak' by manipulating the spatial location of concepts (for example, placing nodes apart would mean that concepts are opposites; on top of each other, that they are subordinated; along a horizontal line, that there is a temporal order, and so on). This way, students use the diagrammatic representation as a generator of ideas to elaborate in the text. In this context, the concept map becomes an abstract machine, in the Deleuzian sense; that is, "a blind and mute machine that makes others see and speak" [1]. At the end of the course, the diagrams with their corresponding texts describing the ideas that the student has discovered in/with them, remain as tangible and permanent manifestations of a knowledge generated out of the concept map.

⁶ As Scardamalia [7] reports from the experience with CSILE, "[The communal database] objectifies knowledge in a way that conventional educational media do not, making it more possible to diffuse knowledge, revise and augment it, and bring it together into larger wholes".

⁷ In McAleese's words, "[In the construction of conceptual maps] learners will come to negotiate and modify what it is that they appear to know in terms of what is known".

7 Discussion

The challenge we are facing as educators in the information age is to interweave technology, knowledge and pedagogy in an innovative and efficient manner. After the experiences of the last decades, it must be clear now that computer technology alone cannot bring about any significant change in education. Educators need to devise conceptual frameworks within which technology becomes pedagogically meaningful. As the work presented here shows, a constructivist pedagogy, coupled with simple but conceptually powerful computer environments, can be the appropriate strategy to achieve a meaningful integration of information and communication technologies in education.

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